

STUDIES WITH RESPECT TO THE IMPACT OF THE START-UP NATION PROGRAM

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Abstract

Purpose – *The paper presents the financing opportunities of SMEs, within a competitive and productive entrepreneurial environment. Entrepreneurship has become the subject of many studies during the last decade and it has been proven that it leads to the increase of economic competitiveness, business development, it creates new jobs and makes the business process more efficient.*

Methodology/approach - *A theoretical research using generous references in the field of entrepreneurship, as well as lots of statistical data.*

Findings – *The objective of the Start-up Nation program to stimulate the establishment of new small and medium enterprises has been reached. This program will stimulate young people to stay in the country and to develop entrepreneurial activities, it will contribute to the creation of new companies in fields of high added value so that Romania's attractiveness within the region will increase. This program will create tomorrow's successful companies that will consolidate the bases of the Romanian economy.*

Research limitations/implications – *The theoretical research is using statistical data up to 2017, this it needs to be updated as soon as those data will be available.*

Practical implications – *The evaluation of this program is set on a series of objectives, such as: the presentation of the SMEs situation before and after the program, identifying the main fields that have been financed, the number of financed projects, the analyses of the way in which the beneficiaries have assumed their duties according to the financing rules.*

Originality/value *Such a study cannot take place without a documentation from pertinent sources according to the purposes of the research.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, Start-up Nation, financing, small and medium enterprises.*

Introduction

At present, entrepreneurship represents one of the most debated themes within the European Union as well as within the entire world. Communities, cities, regions and nations are starting to consider entrepreneurship an engine of economic development, of the increase of the number of jobs and competitiveness of companies, while the program Start-up Nation has all of these objectives.

To understand the applicants and to adjust the financing program to their needs should be a purpose in order to elaborate the next financing guide. The applicants' feedback has a significant contribution to a correct elaboration and a positive direction of the financing scheme; thus it is necessary to study their expectations in order to be able to facilitate fundraising and a successful implementation of business plans.

Start-up Nation is a program that has been elaborated by the Romanian Government, in order to stimulate new small and medium enterprises, and the legislation that regulates it is OUG 10/2017, approved by Law 112/2017.

We will approach as follows the regulations that have been in force during the program's first year of application, that is 2017. The program was submitted to the Ministry of Business Environment, Commerce and Entrepreneurship, through the Territorial Offices for Small and Medium Enterprises and Cooperation.

As it has been mentioned in the previously mentioned norms, the companies that were eligible were those established based on Law 31/1990, the cooperative societies established based on Law 1/2000 as well as the start ups registered according to OUG 6/2011, established by individuals after January the 31st, 2017. All of those had to fulfill the eligibility requirements imposed through legislation in the field of minimis helps, as well as the specific requirements in the case of European funding.

The main objective of the minimis scheme is based on stimulating the establishment and development of small and medium enterprises, the improvement of their economic performances, the creation of new jobs, the insertion on the labor market of the disadvantaged persons, unemployed and young graduates, as well as the increase of investments into new innovative technologies, the scheme being applied in all 8 development regions of the country.

According to the legislation in 2017, the minimis help is up to 200.000lei/beneficiary, representing 100% of the value of eligible expenses to a maxim number of 10.000 beneficiaries per year, the sums being provided from the state's budget and/o external funding.

The program finances the implementation of business plans, in the decreasing order of the scores.

Comparative data on the impact of the Start-up Nation program

Due to the fact that one of the eligibility requirements for applying was that the company should be established after January the 31st, 2017, we have decided to analyze the impact of the program Start-up Nation through the new established firms in the first 6 months of 2017, by making a comparison to the previous two years: 2015 and 2016.

Figure 1: New firms in the first 6 months of 2015, 2016, respectively 2017, at national level

To the data from the National Office of Commerce Register, the number of new companies at national level has increased with 12% compared to 2016.

Figure 2. New firms in the first 6 months of 2015, 2016 and 2017 in Cluj

An increase of new firms during the first 6 months from 2017 can also be noticed in Cluj District. The percentage is 16% compared to the previous period of 2016, while 2015 and 2016 are stable.

Figure 3. Type of firms established between June the 1st – July the 1st, 2017, at national level

The impact of the Start-up Nation program can also be noticed from the number of new firms that have been created during the last month for projects' application.

According to the data supplied by the National Council of Small and Medium Enterprises in Romania, just in June there have been registered a number of 15.877 new firms, most of them being SRL.

With respect to the financed projects, according to aippimm.ro, a number of 8653 projects have been financed, due to the fact that most of the applicants have required the maximum value of 200.000lei. Out of these projects, 3466 have obtained 100 points, 4041 had 95 points, while 1146 projects obtained 90 points.

With respect to the domain of the financed projects, it was mainly IT and production, and also creative industries and services. Among the 3466 projects with 100 points, 452 were IT, while the rest – production. Among the 4041 projects with 95 points, 153 were in IT, 1472 – production and 2416 – creative industries. Among those evaluated at 90 points (1146), 38 of them were in the field of production, 13 in the IT, 83 in creative industries and 1012 in services.

Thus, out of the total of the financed projects, 618 were in IT, 4524 in production, 2499 in creative industries and 1012 in services.

Figure 4. The domains financed through Start-up Nation Romania

As it can be seen in Figure 4, the main field of the projects within Start-up Nation program was production, 52%. This can be explained by the fact that production and IT were the best scored domains, with 40 points. Still, 29% of the financed projects were in the field of creative industries, which had 35 points, while services obtained 30 points. The small number of projects for IT can be explained by the fact that in this field it is difficult to hire disadvantage categories of people, since the level of difficulty is high. This field mainly hires university graduates in the field of computers and programming.

Another thing that needs to be mentioned is the fact that there was no financed project in the field of commerce, due to the fact that they received a very low score.

Also, 77.08% of the projects came from the urban environment, while 22.92% from the rural one. The average age of the entrepreneurs was 36.27 years, and 55.85% of them were men.

In every project, to create new jobs is extremely important, while the Start-up Nation program considers these eligible expenses that can be settled. Most of the applicants stated that they will create 1 or 2 working places within the project, 13 of them declared between 10-43 new jobs, according to startupcafe.ro. Thus, out of the total of financed projects, 20.956 new jobs have been created in the fields such as production, services, creative industries and IT.

Figure 5. The domains with the most new jobs

As it can be noticed in Figure 5, most of the new jobs that have been created through the Star-up Nation program are in the field of production – 54% (being the ones that were scored the best), followed by the creative industries with 23%, then 11% in the field of services and just 3% for IT.

The session for applying to the program has been opened on June the 15th, 2017, 10:00 a.m., until July the 14th, 2017, 20.00p.m., using an electronic application on the site aippimm.ro.

With respect to the dynamics of the applications, it seems that during the first 5 hours since the opening of the site have been registered more than 2000 applicants. At the end of the first day, 700 projects have been registered. After the sixth day there were 1511 projects, while at the end of the first week there were 1844 projects.

On June the 30th, 2017, at the half of the application period, there were 3111 projects and 8000 users with an account.

On July the 6th, 2017, after 3 weeks of the Start-up Nation program, 4389 applicants have been registered and 11.000 user accounts.

Thus, the statistics of the Ministry for the Business Environment, Commerce and Entrepreneurship shows that more than 70% of the business plans have been registered during the last 5 days, respectively 13.477. According to the same source, 34% of the business plans were registered during the last day, meaning 6.539 projects. This shows that the applicants have prepared their business plans until the deadlines.

Discussion and conclusions

According to the data presented, it can be stated that the program's objective to stimulate the establishment of new small and medium enterprises has been reached, since 19.000 new companies applied. Start-up Nation motivates the young people to stay in the country and the develop entrepreneurial activities, it will contribute to the creation of new companies in fields with high added value, thus increasing Romania's attractiveness within the region. This program may create tomorrow's successful companies that will consolidate the bases of the Romanian economy.

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